

GENDER POLICY OF THE ORGANIZATION OF ISLAMIC COOPERATION: PROTECTION OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada hozirgi kunda dunyo hamjamiyati Islom davlatlaridagi inson huquqlariga munosabat, xususan, gender tengligi masalasiga bildirilayotgan tanqidiy qarashlar haqida to'xtalib o'tdik. Xo'sh, bu qay darajada to'g'ri? Ularning bu xatti-harakatlari qay darajada asosga ega? Haqiqatdan, Islomda bu masalaga qay darajada e'tibor qaratilmoqda? Shu va shunga o'xshash savollar javobi va boshqa qo'shimcha faktik hamda mantiqiy asoslar asosida ushbu masalaga oydinlik kiritdik.

Kalit so'zlar: Gender tenglik, Inson huquqlari, Islom Hamkorlik Tashkiloti, Inson huquqlari Umumjahon Deklaratsiyasi, Qohira Deklaratsiyasi.

Аннотация: В данной статье мы остановились на критических взглядах, которые в настоящее время высказывается мировое сообщество на отношение к правам человека в исламских государствах, в частности, на вопрос о гендерном равенстве. Итак, насколько это правда? Насколько оправдано их поведение? Действительно, в какой степени этому вопросу уделяется внимание в Исламе? Мы прояснили этот вопрос, основываясь на ответах на эти и подобные вопросы, а также на других дополнительных фактах и обоснованиях.

Ключевые слова: Гендерное равенство, права человека, Организация исламского сотрудничества, Всемирная Декларация Прав Человека, Каирская декларация.

Abstract In this article, we have focused on the critical views that the world community is currently expressing on the attitude to human rights in Islamic States, in particular, on the issue of gender equality. So, how true is this? How justified is their behavior? Indeed, to what extent is this issue given attention in Islam? We have clarified this issue based on the answers to these and similar questions, as well as other additional facts and justifications.

Keywords: Gender equality, human rights, Organization of Islamic Cooperation, World Declaration of Human Rights, Cairo Declaration.

In the 21st century, human rights reached a high level in its development. Human rights rose to such an extent that the common population were able to freely apply directly to the authorities. Freedom of speech press rose to the heights. By this period, the issue of women's law was raised, which is a special legal problem for our attention center. True, this issue is considered a problem raised in the middle of the 20th century. But it is note worthy that the problem of the XXI century is the fact that the world community claims this right in relation to Islamic States is not provided. As stated above, nowadays the freedom of the press is a guaranteed right. With this, there is no right to criticize the general public, but it should also be noted that women in Islamic states in particular have enough rights in Uzbekistan. The main reason why women in Islamic states are not confused with the general public is our mentality, which has been formed for thousands of years. In this regard, we will cite the following practical activities that have recently taken place in our country. In connection with the United Nations “16 days of active action against Gender-Based Violence” company, the Ministry of Gender Commission, neighborhood and family support of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the United Nations program were presented online consultations of a professional lawyer and psychologist for women in the circle of the joint project “expanding the rights and opportunities of women in public administration and

socio-political. At this point, if we turn to the solution of this issue in the system of not only Uzbekistan, but the entire organization of Islamic Cooperation. Before studying these systems, we knew it was permissible to go through this information, thinking that it would be advisable to get acquainted with the Organization of Islamic Cooperation for a while.

What kind of organization is the organization of Islamic Cooperation itself? Organization of Islamic Cooperation-this organization was founded on September 25, 1969 under the name of the Organization of the Islamic Conference. In 2011, the name of this organization was changed to the name of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation. Initially, the headquarters was located in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, and currently 57 states are members of this organization. Among the same countries, our Uzbekistan is also a member of this organization. The number of countries in observer status is 5, and among these countries we can see such countries as Russia. What is the purpose of this organization? Each organization will have its own goals and objectives, of course. Objectives of the organization of Islamic Cooperation:

- cooperation between muslim countries;;
- achieve sustainable development of member countries;
- activities in cooperation in the international square;
- to implement the general policy of the organization, a meeting of the Council of Ministers of Foreign Affairs is held once a year.

The content of the topic that we are going to discuss today is also located precisely under this fourth goal. The Republic of Uzbekistan has been operating in the activities of this organization since 1995, showing special behavior, characteristic character. Including in 2016, the 43rd session of this organization was held in Tashkent, our capital. Speaking of the fourth goal, we have seen that a one-year policy is defined by the foreign ministers of the member states, so to what extent is this policy focused on the issue of Gender equality that is currently

being emphasized all over the world? It is not a secret for us that not only the Islamic world, but also in Uzbekistan, the right to women, the lack of Gender equality cause a lot of criticism. What, in fact, are these objections appropriate?

At this point, I would like to remind you that states that always come up with a big claim, jar the world with different loud statements, actually turn out to be not guided by these ideas themselves. For example, in countries such as the United States and China, which are accustomed to coming up with many claims that there is no focus on human rights, claiming human rights, there is also the death penalty in practice. And in our republic, from January 1, 2008, the death penalty was abolished, which was one of the great works in the field of human rights. Or if we see the situation of such countries as Russia, the United States, China, France, which have introduced into international law such issues as the non-use of force raised at the level of principle in international law, non-interference in the internal affairs of others.

When we touched on the issue of Gender equality, we decided, first of all, to touch a little on the formation of the idea of gender equality, as well as on the evolution of women's rights. Focusing on the period of the historical formation of man, the first of these, which has gone from the beginning to the beginning of two great periods, is matriarchy that is, when the mother will be the authority, while the second period is the patriarchy that is, the authority of the father. As an initial stage when a person appears is considered a period of matriarchy, the reason for this is also very simple that the first person a newborn knows is his mother. The first affection, the first upbringing, the child receives from the mother. This factor caused the establishment of matriarchy. Human Reproduction and the emergence of other natural factors prompted a man to come to the middle as the head of the family.

In world civilization, in the middle of the 20th century, the problem of human rights rose to its new stage in its development. It was from this period that

the problem of “Gender equality” began to spread widely around the world, which began to take shape early in the late XVIII and early XIX centuries. It reached its peak in the middle of the 20th century, and an international document was adopted on it. It is this international document that first enshrined the issue of gender equality on a legal basis. Well in this aspect, let's also focus on evolution related to gender equality among the peoples of the world. We can see traces of patriarchy in most of Egypt, Mesopotamia, Babylon, Rome, Greece, China, India and a number of urban states of the east, considered the countries of the ancient world. Yes there is no doubt that a large part of the ancient city-states were ruled by men, and in many states a very strict way of life was established in relation to women. In ancient China, a man, among his children, also had the right to sell his woman as a slave.¹

In India there was even the custom of burning his woman alive by adding her to it if the land died before the 16th century that is, the times when our grandfather Babur took the throne of India .Referring to Europe, where those human rights developed, in England men had the right to be the head of the family, as well as to sell their children and wife as slaves, a movement that was suspended through the law of 1805 that limited these actions, but with this the movement did not stop. The facts that a 1931 English man sold his woman for £ 500 are known to us from historical works[5.21]. The same was the case in France, where those human rights reached their peak, which we can see limited through the document “on the mountain of human and civil rights”, adopted after the great French bourgeois revolution. We cannot say that even later in the Napoleon Code of 1804 gave a full-fledged result with a certain emphasis on women's rights. We can also find out that the woman who did the same job and the man received two different salaries that is, the woman who did the same job

¹ Odilqoriyev X.T. Xorijiy Mamlakatlar huquqi, davlati tarixi. – T. Yurist. 2019.

received half the share of the man. On December 10, 1948 to all this the end was put. That is, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights put an end to such misunderstandings.

Well, now let's pay one attention to the evolution of Gender equality in Islam, including women's law in Uzbekistan. Statehood on the territory of Uzbekistan goes back to the IX-VII centuries BC. From this period, a specific state system, a specific mentality arose in this area, women had specific rights. The story of the Tomaris, or the existence of female goddesses in the Zoroastrian religion, which is an ancient religion, given in our ancient legends, serves as evidence of respect and attention to women[6.21]. Even in the era of the rulers of the next land, there were special views on women, which we can find both in minted coins and in inscriptions in various manuscripts. The fact that on the minted coins a picture of the Queen was minted side by side with the ruler, or a ban on calling her married woman by name, inherited from the ancient Turks, is considered a worthy event of praise, which is still preserved among Uzbeks today .² The reason why we call it worthy of praise lies in the fact that it embodies the supreme manifestation of mutual respect.

At the beginning of the VIII century, Islam began to enter the territory of Central Asia. Islam has brought a lot of relief to women these are;

- the girl in the Arabs destroyed the vile of burying the Child Alive[5];
- Christian women, the issue of divorce has arisen, aimed at solving the issue of the inability to divorce from marriage, which is a problem (the problem of living with a man who does not like it for himself) [5.21];
- The woman who came into existence in India has eliminated such vices as the worship of her man³;

² Qadimgi choch tangalarini kuzatadigan bo'lsak bir tomonidan xukmdor va uning xotining yonma yon turgan sur'atini ko'rishimiz mumkin (Matnga)

³ Boburnoma, X.T Odilqoriyev Xorijiy Mamlakatlar huquqi tarixi. Xindistonda erkaklar o'z ayollariga xudo

The concept of dowry has been applied in practice. This concept implies that when a woman enters into marriage, she acquires her own property separately from her husband, and this is freely disposed of by him. If there is a divorce from the marriage, then this property will belong only to the woman. This property is considered an increased property, and tomorrow a woman will have the right to freely dispose of it, even in the case when she lived in marriage[6.102].

The topic of the article is also about the view of Islam on the right of women, the issues of Gender equality of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, which is operating today, are being harshly criticized by the general public. Directly before substantiating the norms of human rights, gender equality tables, we preferred to look into their history. From the emergence of statehood forms above, we stopped talking about the establishment of Islamic law, as well as the facts about its wide opportunities for women. If we reflect on the reasons why the public should stop saying that women's rights in Islam are being violated. While Islam came into existence at the beginning of the 7th century, in the following centuries it developed greatly this development continued until the 17th centuries. In the middle of this period, no system could be equated with Islam in the issue of respect for Women, protection of women's rights. In their opposition to the achievements of various sciences in order to preserve power.

Individuals brought up under the ideas of Islam have a relatively oppressive naturalness, as well as difficulty tolerance, this factor prevented the emergence of revolutions in contrast to the European World. It is also important to note that the unfulfilled existence of these revolutions is relatively lighter than that of other religions, and not only because of the right of women, but also because of their great importance to human rights in general, and that is why the revolutions did

sifatida talqin etilgan er vafot etsa ayol ham yashash huquqini yo'qotgan va unga qo'shilib tiriklay yonishga majbur bo'lishgan.

not materialize. The reason why we say that the revolutions were unfulfilled is that Islam did not put too much pressure and that people did not have the need to raise their heads in relation to religion.

By the middle of the 20th century, human problems in international law were raised to a new level, especially the problem of gender equality. In particular, in the " Universal Declaration of Human Rights " these rights went to find their reflection. It is known from history that the shameless battles in the XIX-XX century to conquer the world began to lag behind in the development of Islamic States as a result of specific political games. Even so, by the middle of the 20th century, most Islamic states were holding their independence in their hands . The outbreak of the Cold War caused some inconvenience to all Islamic states, including the Arab ones. Under such conditions, the Organization of Islamic Cooperation arose in 1969. The emergence of this organization was an excessive headache for states that sought to politically control some world. What to do in such a situation? It is necessary to look for excuses and shortcomings to condemn the organization. One of these shortcomings was the attitude of Islam towards women. Islam, which once brought enlightenment relief to women of peoples who were experiencing difficulties in all religions, now seemed to have become a mechanism that violates women's rights as if. This was also the product of the fact that even higher it was precisely some fanatics who reacted unilaterally to religious norms in fact. The "Gender Equality" relations of the Islamic Cooperation Organization are reflected in the "Cairo Declaration on Human Rights". As we read these norms, we can see that the issues that are exaggerated by critics, are not really a serious risk to this extent. In particular, if we consider on the basis of the norms of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights Article 12 describes " arbitrary interference in anyone's personal and family life, the inviolability of housing, the secrets of his correspondence or his honor and honor cannot be assaulted in my own head. Everyone has the right to be protected by

law from similar interference or aggression.” So states that have increased this type of behavior should not interfere in matters related to the family and or honor of the peoples of Islam. Regarding Gender equality, we can cite the norms of the following articles of the Cairo Declaration Article 6 “A woman is equal to a man in terms of human dignity”, Article 11 “people are born free and no one can treat a second person as a slave”.

These factors lead to the need for additional mechanisms for maintaining public order, including the search for the creation of public or public-state organizations of Citizens for the protection of Public Order and formalization in legislation[8] .⁴

If we pay attention to history, analyze and observe it even now, we can see the rights of women that are inherent in public administration as well as in relations in society. See, for example, the account of women's weight in the Parliament of the countries of the world.

- Uzbekistan-32%
- USA-19,1 %
- Russia - 15,8 %

It can also be seen here how much the deputy women's weight in Uzbekistan, which is an organization of Islamic Cooperation, is more than the deputy women's weight in those countries that are accused of gender equality. It is considered a concept that refers to the disclosure of broad preferences to women, not gender equality. Islamic states in particular, Uzbekistan protects women's rights not only from the point of view of the law, but also in a situation that arises from the criteria of Justice.

⁴Alimov Muxiddin Ilxomjon o'g'li. (2022). Participation of Citizens in the Maintenance of Public Order Historical-Theoretical Significance. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 13, 67–70. Retrieved from <https://www.zienjournals.com/index.php/jpip/article/view/2588>

In conclusion, the world community condemns the relationship of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation to women's rights. But not every argument shows that Islam does not restrict women's rights, but that some countries are pursuing their wrong policy by sticking to certain norms, but states that understand the true nature of Islam should say such things, but also be ashamed that they have come to this imagination.

In addition to the fact that every muslim countries shows its legal basis that women's rights are protected in the country, it is necessary to point out the criteria for justice to the general public. In this case, it is necessary to widely promote various articles on this topic, as well as videos, various shows. It is necessary to spread more widely his thoughts on this mountain of perfect people who are true Muslims. Explaining the characteristics of Islamic culture to the general public in order to show the world community that the passivity of women in Muslim countries is not a violation of women's rights, but a kind of form of mentality, moral norms that have been formed for thousands of years. To do this, it is necessary to bring this area to the world education system. It can be attributed not for the purpose of religious education, but as an effort to preserve the norms of morality in society.

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